

Psychological Burnout Among Faculty Members In The College Of Basic Education

Fatima Adel Dakel Isa

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: October 02, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: November 19, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Psychological Burnout, Faculty Members, College Of Basic Education</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4281133</p>	<p><i>Burnout is a feeling of helplessness, fatigue, and exhaustion due to excessive demands as a result of an individual performing his skills. The current research is limited to the teaching staff of the College of Basic Education / University of Maysan for the academic year 2018-2019. Initially, the researcher prepared an exploratory questionnaire to know the level of psychological burnout among the faculty members in the College of Basic Education. - Research community: The current research community consists of faculty members in the College of Basic Education. - The sample: I used a random sample consisting of (40) female and male faculty members. Search tool: The questionnaire was adopted as a tool to achieve the objectives of the research, and previous studies. The results of the research were statistically treated using the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, variance, the calculated T, and the tabular T value. The researcher reached some recommendations and suggestions, including: Paying attention to the faculty members from all sides because their sense of attention and support reduces psychological burnout. Conducting a study on psychological burnout according to the variable of years of service and academic specialization.</i></p>

1. Introduction

(Fardin Brucker) showed that the professions most exposed to psychological burnout are the service professions in general and professions in the field of human service in particular (Fardin Brucker, 1974: 14). Studies have found that, in most cases, what increases the probability of leaving workers in the social and educational field and in rehabilitation services Care for their jobs and their work is doubled compared to other professions as a result of this phenomenon. Therefore, the percentage of those who quit their jobs between 25% and 30%, while the percentage of those leaving in other professions did not range between 8% or 15%. (1986: 62, sealge)

The American National Education Association indicated that a third of the teachers who were selected in the study showed symptoms of burnout through their answer that if they began their lives again, they would not choose a teaching profession. It emerged that 20% to 60% of them were suffering from burnout and that 41% Of the teachers in New York suffered from physical and mental exhaustion as a result of their work, which led to some of them leaving the teaching profession, for example in 1961 28% of teachers had 20 years of educational service, while this number decreased by half in 1967 (Farber, 1984: 325)

Many specialists agreed that psychological burnout is a comprehensive negative effect that deals with the individual completely, not only on the psychological side, but also on the physical side, which negatively affects the performance of individuals and workers in every field (Truck-s, 1980: 10)

While a number of researchers have concluded that psychological burnout is an organizational and personal problem together, as it often has a negative impact on individuals and the services they provide. They are often absent from work, family problems and lack of clarity, in addition to various psychological and physical disorders (pierce, C.and molly, G 1990 sp 114).

Mesilk, (1981, p107) emphasized in his study that psychological burnout may constitute a state of emotional exhaustion represented by loss of hope, feeling depressed, physical and mental effort, and acting negatively towards self, others, and public life.

There are many reasons, including work pressure, economic and social problems, and guest dissatisfaction. Work pressure has direct negative effects on an individual's physical and mental health, and the greater the risk of developing cardiovascular disease and stomach disease, and a lot of psychological symptoms, anxiety, feelings of frustration and depression, which leads to a decrease in work productivity. Poor performance and absence, and endangers the lives and safety of others (Askar, 1988: 8).

Burnout is a disease characterized by a set of signs, symptoms, and changes in professional and physical behavior in some people with this disease. According to this case of fatigue within a category of psychosocial-occupational diseases due to its being the result of exposure to permanent and prolonged pressures, this case in

English is called (Burnout), hence the expression psychological burnout is death resulting from excessive workloads.

Hence, it can be said that psychological burnout is a real problem facing the faculty member who is the means by which the goals of the university in which he works are achieved, and who is asked to perform various tasks and roles in order to achieve them, as he deals with work as a teacher, administrative and others in order to be able to perform this task easily and competently And in a good way without providing the home environment and the means that help in reaching the desired goals, and thus the faculty member represents a sensitive position in the educational process.

It is directed at the educational process, because any defect that affects him leads to an imbalance in the entire educational process. If the faculty member is not in a normal situation, the educational process will crack, and this of course will reflect on the whole society.

The danger is when a faculty member suffers from psychological burnout because this will negatively affect the health and psychological situation, the institution in which he works, as well as the students who deal with them. If the faculty member is psychologically burned, then he becomes ineffective and his commitment to his work is low.

Research importance:

The importance of the research lies in the fact that the teaching profession is one of the most prominent professions in the human service that increase the likelihood of its workers being exposed to psychological combustion, especially as it requires great energy and mental effort and emotional balance in the era of the information revolution that is reflected in all aspects of the human personality. That is why he described our era as an era of stress and psychological crises, until some researchers termed the diseases of civilization caused by a contemporary society full of conflicts, ambitions and social problems. (Paul and fellow Eret 1990)

The teaching has an effective role in the educational process, so any negative effects on the teaching will negatively affect the entire educational process. Psychological combustion is one of the phenomena with negative effects in dealing with others.

Thus, the teacher represents one of the important factors in the success of any educational process, and this requires its owner to be characterized by sufficient and abundant competence and skills in order to practice his profession properly and appropriately. (The Sheiks, 2008: 122)

No educational system can perform its desired role in the best way without a qualified instructor. The university, as a tool of education, cannot achieve its desired goals unless it is directed towards upgrading the level of preparation and qualification of teachers and turning them into educators and mentors for students (Al-Tamimi, 2001: 201). The phenomenon of teaching psychological burnout overlaps with other intertwined thoughts, including social and university authority, and perhaps the teaching trend towards the profession and the main determinant of his endurance to the profession and its psychological and physical pressures, and consequently to the psychological burnout that he faces, is the key word for the teaching success in his work is its positive trends Towards the mission. Because these trends are the basis on which most educational activities are built (Chase, 1985: pp12-18). Hence, it can be said that the university is one of the institutions that have the forefront in society because it is the center for preparing generations of learners and therefore it is a center of radiance for every new thought, knowledge and platform that It prepares categories of educated, educated and future scholars.

Research objective:

Learning about psychological burnout among faculty members of the College of Basic Education

Research journals:

Spatial domain: College of Basic Education / University of Maysan

Temporal domain: 2018-2019

- The human field: members of the faculty in the College of Basic Education / University of Maysan

Defining terms:

Burnout is defined by:

- Webster Dictionary (1989): that it is the feeling of helplessness, exhaustion, and exhaustion due to excessive demands as a result of the individual's performance of his skill.

- Truch, (1980: 4): defined it as Physical and Emotional Exhaustion Plus: a type of chronic stress reaction with a long-term negative impact. (Assaf. A. M. 1987: 279)

- Odeh (1998) defined it as the state of psychological and physical fatigue appears on the individual as a result of work pressure to which he is exposed and affects his direction towards the profession in which he works.

Theoretical framework:

1- What is burnout?

No one knew anything about the phenomenon of burnout before the clinical psychologist, Fredid Nberger (1974) published his first work on this topic in a scientific interview in which he described

psychological burnout as a state of weakness, fatigue and exhaustion resulting from the inability of human service workers to deal With many demands on their energies, powers and resources (Al-Atabi, 2003).

2- Burnout symptoms:

- Failure, exhaustion and exhaustion
- Loss of the ability to innovate
- Lack of loyalty to work
- A state of aversion to auditors, colleagues, and the job
- Strong response to stress
- Negative attitudes towards clients and a psychological trend accompanied by uncomfortable physical and emotional symptoms (Al-Jaafari, 2005: 5)

3- Causes of psychological burnout:

Jumah Yusuf (2006) describes the causes of psychological burnout that most of them are related to the work environment and the opportunities it provides that help maximize the levels of pressure, frustration and oppression for long periods of time. These reasons can be summarized in:

Excessive workload

- clerical work

Shallow reach and poor return

- Loss of a sense of control over work outcomes

Monotony and boredom at work (Yusef, 2006: 40)

4- Burnout stages:

According to Matte son & Ivancevich, (1987), the phenomenon of burnout does not happen suddenly, but rather includes the following stages:

Involvement:

In it, the level of job satisfaction is high, but if there is a mismatch between what is expected of work and what is actually happening, the level of satisfaction begins to decrease.

Stagnation:

This stage grows slowly, and the level of job satisfaction gradually decreases, efficiency decreases, the level of performance at work decreases, and the individual feels moderate in his physical health and transfers his interest to other aspects of life, such as hobbies and social contacts, in order to occupy leisure time.

Detachment:

And in detachment it, the individual realizes what has happened, and begins to withdraw psychologically, and moderate physical and psychological health, with the high level of psychological stress

Critical Juncture:

It is the most extreme stage in the chain of psychological burnout, in which the physical, psychological, and behavioral symptoms increase, bad and dangerous, and the individual's thinking is the result of self-doubt, and the individual reaches the stage of conquest (explosion) and thinks about leaving work and may think about suicide (Zaidan, 1998: 11)

5- Burnout levels:

Spaniel (1979) indicated that burnout feelings are associated with the pattern (routine) of work, and he has identified three levels:

A- Mild burnout:

It results in short bouts of fatigue, anxiety, frustration, and irritability

B- Neutral burnout:

It results in the same previous symptoms, but it lasts for at least two weeks

C - Severe psychological burnout:

It results in severe symptoms such as ulcers, chronic back pain, and severe headaches, and it is not surprising that the faculty members feel feelings of moderate and moderate psychological burnout from time to time, but when these feelings persist and appear in the form of chronic physical and psychological diseases then burning becomes a serious problem. (Badran, 1997: 58)

6- Dimensions of psychological burnout:

According to Maslash et al. (1978-1976), the collision of stressful professions causes feelings of intense and permanent tension with people that lead to loss of interest and lack of commitment, which are opposite to the professor's original directions and these feelings appear in three dimensions:

Emotional attrition:

Since the emotional feelings have been depleted, the teaching staff cannot or do not have the ability to give as they were before, and this poet is represented in the intensity of tension and stress and the teacher's feeling that he has nothing left to give to others on the psychological level

Loss of instantaneous:

And clarifies the negative trends the direction of those who work with them, the burned teacher psychologically, and these negative trends, which are sometimes sarcastic (sarcastic) do not represent the distinctive features of the teaching.

Lack of personal achievement:

This dimension occurs when individuals begin to evaluate themselves negatively, when they lose enthusiasm for achievement and when the teacher feels that he is no longer competent in working with his students and his inability to fulfill his other responsibilities (Badran, 1997)

Theories and models explaining psychological combustion

Chernys burnout model:

Cherniss, (1985) presented the comprehensive model of psychological combustion, and he met with his assistants twenty-eight professionals in four fields: the field of health, the field of law, the field of nursing in public hospitals, and the field of teaching in secondary schools, and all the subjects were interviewed several times during a period ranging from One to two years, and the following figure shows the Chernes model.

Tsherence explained that the greater the shock of reality and the greater the exposure to stress, the greater the psychological burnout, and the model also indicated that people who get high scores in psychological burnout are those who receive weak social support .

The model also shows that demographic factors such as age, gender, and years of experience are poorly related to burnout (Badran, 1997).

Accordingly, according to the model, those who obtain high burnout scores are the teaching staffs who feel psychosomataical symptoms, and they are the ones who use drugs increasingly, and suffer from marital dissatisfaction, role conflict, lack of job satisfaction, and higher absenteeism rates, and they tend to quit the profession.

Previous studies:-

1- Arabic Studies:

A- The Study of Alkaser, (1993):

-Variables of psychological burnout for middle school teachers and the role of instructional intervention.

Alkaser, (1993) conducted a study to identify the specific variables of combustion by finding the relationship between their scores on the combustion scale and their scores on the work stress scale and methods of dealing with stress, as well as the variables of sex, age, marital status, length of service, and after-work work.

The study sample included (320) teachers and one from secondary and intermediate schools in Baghdad.

The results of the study have shown that the increase in stored and uncontrolled stresses may make the teacher burn more likely and vice versa, as the challenge to the stress often increases the combustion, as well as the method of acceptance and neglect interacting with the stresses of conflict within the work may increase the possibility of the emergence of psychological combustion.

B- The study of Mahdi, (2001):

He investigated the relationship of self-concept to the phenomenon of psychological burnout among teachers in the Faculties of Physical Education in Iraq. The study aimed to:

- Identify the self-concept of the teaching staff in the Faculties of Education in the universities of Mosul, Baghdad and Basra.
- To know the level of psychological burnout of the teaching staff in the colleges of sports education in the universities of Mosul, Baghdad and Basra

The sample has reached (150) teachers who represent the teaching of sports education colleges for the universities of (Mosul - Baghdad - Basra). The Tennessee Self-Concept Scale (t.s.c.s) and the Psychological Burnout Scale for the teachers were used, and the most important conclusions of the study were the following:

- There are significant differences between the teachers in the universities of Mosul, Baghdad and Basra in each of the dimensions of the moral self, the personality, the self-criticism, and the adamic self.
- There are significant differences between the teachers from the universities of Mosul, Baghdad and Basra in the intensity of the feeling of psychological burnout, where the intensity of the feeling of psychological burnout was high for the teaching staff in the universities of Mosul and Baghdad compared to the teaching staff at the University of Basra. (Mahdi, 2001)

C- The study of Al-Attayah and Issawi (2004):

The study aimed to identify the level of psychological burnout of a sample of female workers with special needs in the State of Qatar, and its relationship to some variables (gender, age, marital status, academic qualification, years of experience, type of work, type of relationship).

The sample of the study consisted of (138) female workers with special needs in the State of Qatar (Qatari and non-Qatari)

The study used the Maslach scale of psychological burnout among workers in the field of human and social services.

The study found the following results: There is a moderate level of psychological burnout among female workers with special needs in the State of Qatar.

- The presence of statistically significant differences between Qatari women and non-Qatari women in psychological combustion in the sense of achievement, and the overall degree, in favor of the Qatari women.
- The presence of statistically significant differences between the different age levels in psychological burnout, in favor of the different age group in psychological burnout, in favor of the age group less than 30 years old.
- The presence of statistically significant differences between married and unmarried women in the psychological burnout after the lack of a sense of achievement and emotional stress, and the overall degree in favor of unmarried women.
- The presence of statistically significant differences between the different levels of experience in psychological burnout, in favor of years of experience of less than 5 years in the dimension of emotional stress and the overall degree.
- The presence of statistically significant differences between those with different qualifications in psychological burnout in favor of those with high school education in the dimension of emotional stress, lack of a sense of achievement and the overall degree.
- There were no significant differences in psychological burnout according to the type of disability.

Foreign Studies:

A- The study of Ewe ,(1998):

The study was conducted in England

The study aimed to examine the relationship between middle school teacher burnout, stress, job satisfaction, and coping methods, the number of participants in this study (220) middle school teacher in England. The participants answered on the surveys, levels of burnout, stress, job satisfaction, coping methods, and provided demographic information, including gender, age, and years of experience.

The results indicated:

- Occupational stress and problem-focused adaptation were important indicators of triple burnout
- Teachers who cite greater stress also indicated higher levels of emotional fatigue and lower levels of personal achievement.
- Use of adaptation focuses on the problem; it is linked negatively to emotional fatigue and lower levels of personal achievement

Teacher burnout, job pressure, and coping methods did not differ with regard to age and gender variables

- Job satisfaction is negatively associated with emotional burnout. (Way, 1998)

B –The study of Annette's study, (1999):

The study was conducted in the United States of America

This study compared the level of job satisfaction and psychological burnout among teachers working in special education in the high school student and the ease of public accommodation for students and the development of disability in Al-Masabi in the United States. The researcher used the Minnesota questionnaire

for satisfaction (short form) and the scale (Maslach for intellectuals 1986), which was used to compare the burnout levels in two groups, psychological burnout was measured through three dimensions, which are emotional exhaustion, dullness of feeling, and personal achievement.

The results indicated that there were important differences in the levels of major and emergency job satisfaction between two groups, while no statistically significant differences appeared between the two groups regarding psychological burnout (Annette, 1999).

C- The study of Jill ,(2000):

The study was conducted in California. This study investigated the relationship between expectations of negative mood regulation, job stress, coping, depression, and burnout among teachers

The number of participants in this study reached (93) teachers from (6) schools in California, where the teachers answered the teacher pressure list, the bad mood regulation scale, the adaptation scale, the burnout Maslach list, the praise of the educators, and the short list of symptoms.

Where the results indicated that the expectations of negative mood regulation have distinctively predicted the occurrence of adaptation, depression and psychological burnout in a way that exceeds what the stress only expects. Also, it was found that expectations of negative mood regulation are positively related to positive adaptation and negatively to avoidant adaptation.

It also indicated that teachers with high results in negative mood regulation indicated lower levels of psychological burnout and depression, and this study confirms the validity of the negative mood regulation scale in predicting adaptation, depression and psychological burnout. The negative mood regulation scale can be an effective tool in identifying teachers who have them, Expecting of low negative mood regulation so that intervention programs can or target those who may be affected by burnout.

- Research Methodology:

The nature of the problem to be studied determines the research method used (Al-Muhammadawi, 2012, p. 42)

Therefore, we chose the descriptive approach as it fits the nature of the problem at hand.

- Research community:

The current research community consists of professors of the College of Basic Education, Misan University, who number (75) teaching staff members for the academic year (2018-2019).

- The research sample:

The research sample was chosen randomly, which consists of (40) teachers from the faculty members of the College of Basic Education and those distributed to the departments (first grades teacher, Arabic language, English language, history, geography, art education, mathematics) and the percentage was (53%) which from the research community.

Table 1

Study community	Study sample	%
75	40	53%

Research instrument:

After reviewing a set of measures of psychological burnout in scientific sources, the scale (Al-Qaryouti and Abdel-Fattah, 1998) was chosen by the researcher

Scale design:

The scale consists of (34) paragraphs and three alternatives to the answer, which are (always, sometimes, rarely) and give (3) scores from the first alternative (always) and (2) two degrees for the second alternative (sometimes) and (1) a score for the third alternative.

Psychometric properties of scale:

Validate scale:

Validity is one of the basic psychometric properties of the scale because it reveals the scale's ability to measure what it is set for.

(Back, 1993: 383)

A delegation we relied on the apparent sincerity of the insulting of the appropriateness of the scale instructions and its paragraphs and the alternatives to the answer. We presented the scale to a group of experts and in light of their observations it was found that the scale instructions, paragraphs and alternatives are appropriate and clear to the teacher that all the paragraphs had the approval of all experts without deleting any paragraph or amendment.

Reliability of scale:

The reliability of the scale under study was found, as stability is one of the most important characteristics of a good test, and the test consistency is intended (to give the same results if it is re-applied to the same sample in two different periods and in similar circumstances) and stability is expressed by the stability factor (which is a form of the correlation coefficient Between the test results in two consecutive periods) as the stability factor of the scale was calculated by the method (test and usually test application). (Al-Muhammadawi, 2012, p. 51)

And after processing the data obtained from the two tests in light of calculating the simple correlation coefficient (Pearson) between the test scores and the test reliability was (0.79) and this is a medium correlation coefficient, because (the closer the value to (± 1) means the strong correlation and vice versa the further away the value is from (± 1 means weak correlation).

1- Statistical methods: (arithmetic mean, standard deviation, variance, computed T-value, tabulated T-value)

Presentation and analysis of results: -

This chapter deals with presenting the statistical results that resulted from the research on the study of psychological burnout among faculty members. The statistical results showed that the arithmetic mean reached (61.18) and the standard deviation (6.59). Significance (0.05) and the degree of freedom was (38.39) as in Table No. (3)

Table 2

الدالة	القيمة التانية الجدولية	القيمة التانية المحسوبة	درجة الحرية	التباين	الانحراف المعياري	الوسط الحساب	العدد
دالة	2.02	6.56	39	43.39	6.59	61.18	40

No	Mean	S.D	variance	D.F	computed T-value	tabulated T-value	Sig level
40	61.18	6.59	43.39	39	6.56	2.02	sig

The statistical results in the above table indicate that there is a significant difference between the calculated T value and the tabular T value. This means that the level of psychological burnout among the members of the research sample is generally high

High psychological burnout: It results in physical symptoms, ulcers, chronic back pain, severe headaches, and it is not uncommon for faculty members to feel feelings of moderate and moderate psychological burnout from time to time, but when these feelings persist and appear in the form of chronic physical and psychological diseases then the burning becomes Serious problem (Badran, 1997)

Conclusions:

The presence of psychological burnout among the faculty members

- The presence of psychological burnout among the faculty members, at a very low rate

Recommendations:

- Paying attention to the faculty members from all sides because their sense of attention and support reduces psychological burnout

- Work by the scientific departments on seminars about the nature of the work of the teachers and their encouragement and appreciation for their efforts exerted in the scientific process.

Suggestions:

- Conducting a study on psychological burnout according to the variable of years of service and academic specialization
- Conducting a comparative study in psychological burnout among teacher
- Conducting a study to find out the relationship between psychological burnout and work satisfaction for the teaching staff of the Faculty of Basic Education, University of Misan.

References

- Badran, Mona Muhammad Ali (1997), Psychological burnout among secondary school teachers and its relationship to some variables, field study, unpublished master's thesis, Institute of Educational Studies and Research, Cairo University.
- Al-Tamimi, Awad Jassim, (2001), The Competencies of the Basic Education Teacher, a paper presented to the First National Conference on Educational Sciences at Al-Mustansiriya University, p.20.
- Al-Jaafari, Abd al-Latif (2005), Psychological Burnout of Persons with Special Needs, its fortune for educational and psychological sciences.
- Zidan, Iman Muhammad Mustafa (1998), The effectiveness of both directed and non-directed psychological counseling in alleviating the psychological burnout among a sample of female teachers, unpublished PhD thesis, Institute of Educational Studies and Research, Cairo University.
- Alshuok, Ghassan Saeed (2008), Obstacles to the use of included learning from the viewpoint of faculty members in the Faculties of Teacher Education, in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.
- Askar, Ali-and others (1986), Extent of exposure of secondary school teachers in the State of Kuwait to increased psychological burnout, The Educational Journal of the College of Education, Kuwait University, No. 10, The Third Skin, p. 8.
- Othman, Farouk El-Sayed (2001), Anxiety and Stress Management, Arab Thought House, 1st floor, Cairo.
- Al-Attayah, Asma and Issawi, Tariq (2004), Psychological burnout among a sample of female workers with special needs and its relationship to some variables in the State of Qatar, The Egyptian Journal of Psychological Studies, April Issue 45.
- Odeh, Ahmad Salman, Measurement and Evaluation in the Teaching Process, p. 21, Dar Al-Amal, Jordan 1993.
- Al-Atabi, Adam Ghazi (2003), Occupational burnout among workers in the private sector and its relationship to personality type, Journal of Social Sciences, Kuwait.
- Al kaser, Ibrahim and Abdel-Fattah, Faisal (1998), Psychological burnout among a sample of teachers of ordinary students and teachers of students with special needs in the United Arab Emirates, College Journal, UAE Collectors, 15, 95-134.
- Al-Qusayr, Muhammad Jassim (1993), The Limited Variables of Psychological Burnout for Middle School Teachers and the Role of Instructional Intervention, Ibn Rushd College of Education, Unpublished Master's Thesis.
- Al-Muhammadawi, Haider Abd al-Wahid, The Relationship of Multidimensional Anxiety with the Performance of Some Offensive Skills among Football Players, Unpublished Master Thesis, Al-Mustansiriya University, College of Basic Education, 2012.
- Mahdi, Soha Hafez Ibrahim (2001), the relationship of self-concept to the phenomenon of psychological burnout among teachers in the College of Physical Education in Iraq, Master Thesis, College of Physical Education, University of Baghdad.
- Youssef, Gomaa Sayed (2006), Work Stress Management, Cairo, Center for Postgraduate Studies and Research Development, Faculty of Engineering, Cairo University.
- Assaf .A. (1989) faculty members and burnout in tow major west bank universities dissertate abstract international (50) (3) 279
- Angel, p : Anton , a-8 jonnop (2003) : burnout syndrome and coping – strategies , astrutual – relation aodel – psychology in Spain , rolz nj , p 46, 55.
- Chase , c.1. two thousand teachers their profession journal of education , vol 79 , no. 1 , pp 12-18
- Cain , Gill , (2000) teacher burnout the relationship expectancies , stress mood , and distress pro quest dissertation abstract California state university , degree : MS , pp :55
- Freuden Berger H . staff burnout journal of social is seas vol . 50 No . 1,1 a 74
- Faber B – A (1984) teacher burnout assumption myths and issues teacher college record 86 (2) , 321-38
- Jones Sunday Annette , (1990) A comparing of job employed Mississippi public schools and public redid entail facilities for students developmental disabilities ,pro degree : phd , pp :87
- Konert , Ewa , (1998) the relationship among middle school teacher burnout stress , job satisfaction and coping styles pro quest dissertatation abstracts way in state university degree : phd , pp : 196
- Maslash C. and Jackson – s (1981) burnout inventory manual , Palo Alio , counseling psychatigist press
- Pierce – and molley G .(1990)

Psychological and biographical differences between secondary school teachers experiencing high and low levels, of burnout British journal educational psychology

Powell enriggid – s – (1990) Anxiety and stress management Rutledge N . X

Seagle E .E (1986) faculty in the California state university system dissertation abstract later national 42 (q2) , 438 A

Truch – s – teacher burn out , Novate calf academy 1980

Author Information

Dr. Fatima Adel Dakel Isa

Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific
Research , University of Misan Faculty of Basic
Education , First Grades Teacher Department
